

Innovation Activities and Employment Level: An Empirical Assessment of Russian Manufacturing Companies

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Abstract: The study analysis the impact of innovation on employment in Russian industry. Because innovation, by nature, has an oppositely directed influence on employment level, the impact of product and process innovations is considered separately. To this end, we study overcompensate and displacement effects. The first one refers to the replacement of labour with technology, and the second one refers to the growth of employment caused by the emergence of product innovation and the corresponding expansion of production. It is found that the growth in costs of process innovation causes a decrease in employment and the increase in innovative production (product innovation) positively affects the level of employment.

Keywords: innovation, employment, labour, industry, Russia

1. Introduction

Even though a steady positive impact of innovation on long-term economic growth has been established, there is still no answer to the question of how innovation processes affect employment levels in the economy. A considerable amount of scientific research is devoted to this problem (Вешкурова et al, 2017; Entorf and Pohlmeier, 1990; Lachenmaier and Rottmann, 2011). The difficulties are largely because innovation, because of its nature, has two impacts on economic employment (Harrison et al, 2014, 2008; Greenan and Guellec, 2011). On the one hand, new technologies replace the use of labor in production processes, and on the other hand, their use leads to increased demand for new products (Moon, 2008; Kwon et al, 2015). The latter encourages firms to expand production, resulting in increased demand for manpower. In other words, innovation, even by releasing labour through displacement effects, can generate additional growth for these resources through the emergence and/or expansion of new products. Therefore, the result is not predetermined and depends on the relationship between the displacement effect and overcompensate effect. Since the theory does not allow to determine this ratio due to the difficulty of predicting the variants of technological development, it is possible to determine how much one of these effects dominates the other only after the application of empirical methods.

From what has just been said, it follows that the displacement and overcompensate effects are generated by different types of innovation: process and product innovation. This is reflected in the different objectives for which firms use these types of innovations (Капелюшников, 2017). Process innovations are designed to improve the production process, in particular, to increase productivity and reduce cost. In a competitive environment, the reduction in the cost of production encourages the producer to reduce the price of the product and thus increases its demand. Growth of demand issue the challenge of expansion of manufacture, i.e. attraction of an additional labour force, if productivity growth does not allow to solve a problem of manufacture expansion completely. That is, along with the displacement effect there is an overcompensate effect (Seidl da Fonseca, 2017). Product innovation has a significant impact on the development of the overcompensate effect. If such innovation is introduced in the existing market, then, by expanding the demand for an improved product, it leads to the expansion of production, i.e. employment growth. When product innovation generates a new market, they trigger additional demand for labour. To meet this demand, it is necessary to either relocate labour from existing markets or involve a new resource that has not yet been used. In the first case, the effect of increasing employment will not work, and in the second case, it might be very significant.

It should also be noted that in some cases process innovations may not cause an overcompensate effect even with significant displacement. In other words, cost reduction may lead to the substitution of labour resources and may not contribute to production expansion (Balycheva and Samovoleva, 2019). This situation arises in monopolistic (Vivarelli, 2014) or oligopolistic markets. At the same time, an overcompensate effect arises when

a decrease in production costs leads to a decrease in prices and, accordingly, to an increase in demand. It follows from the above that when studying the impact of innovation on employment, the degree of monopolization of markets should be taken into account. The presence of this effect is indirectly reflected in the significant scale of production, which exceeds the amounts needed to achieve optimal productivity and efficiency in the production process. In many activities, large scale production is often associated with the need to optimize the production process. At the same time, however, firms that have reached this level have prerequisites for taking a monopolistic position. One of the indicators of using innovation to strengthen their monopolistic position is the active use of process innovation.

Thus, as a working hypothesis, we can consider that the indicators of the presence of displacement and overcompensate effects are, respectively, the scale of product and process innovation using. These scales, as practice shows, largely depend on the specifics of activities, market structure and the degree of competition. For this reason, this paper looks at the impact of innovation activity on employment changes in the economy, taking into account the type of activity and the type of innovation applied. The impact of product and process innovation on the change in employment levels in different activities is examined separately.

2. Data and methods

The paper uses the data of the Russian Federal State Statistical Service for 2010-2016, published in the collections "Industrial production in Russia, 2016", as well as on the official website of the Unified information system for the Ministry of Education and Science of the Russian Federation.

When building an econometric model, the employment growth rate was used as a dependent variable, taking into account the type of economic activity. To assess the impact of changes in demand for labour caused by the production of old products, the indicator of growth in this output was chosen as an independent variable. In order to assess the impact of innovation activity in the introduction and diffusion of new products, the growth of innovation output was considered. This is a key indicator for assessing the impact of product innovation on employment change (Harrison et al, 2014). An analysis of the impact of process innovation is proposed based on the indicator of unit costs of process innovation. The increase in unit costs of machinery and equipment in the cost of technological innovation is used as an additional indicator to assess the trend towards a renewal of production processes and overall production expansion. To assess the propensity of firms to develop and implement new products and methods of production, the indicator of unit costs for research and development of new products, services and methods of their production in the costs of technological innovation was taken into account. Also, the cost of technological innovation is considered as an independent variable. In the following, indicators will be discussed separately and the main results of the econometric analysis will be presented.

3. General characteristics of employment and innovation in Russian economy

The overall innovative activity of Russian industrial enterprises is low. For most industries, the share of sales of innovative products in all sales is less than 5% and for only a small part of the activities this indicator exceeds 20% (see Fig. 1). This situation is related to high risks and low business interest in the implementation of innovative projects (Balycheva and Golichenko, 2015; Samovoleva and Balycheva, 2018).

Figure 1: Share of sales of innovative products among all sales of industrial enterprises (2010-2015)

At the same time, most industries are characterized by an increase in the production of innovative products compared to the previous period (see Fig. 2).

Figure 2: Distribution of sales growth of innovative products compared to the previous period (2010-2015)

The low output of innovative products indicates a low tendency of firms to introduce product innovations, which usually lead to higher employment levels. However, companies may be actively involved in the implementation of process innovations to optimize the innovation process and reduce the cost of earlier products. Thus, investments of Russian industrial firms in process innovations are higher than investments in product innovations (see Fig. 3). At the same time, it can be noted that most activities are focused on one type of innovation activity, either companies are engaged in product or process innovations.

Figure 3: Distribution of costs of process (purple) and product innovations (pink) of Russian industrial enterprises (2010-2015), million rubles

The required number of employees at the enterprise to produce equal value products varies greatly depending on the type of economic activity (see Fig. 4). For example, to produce a unit of production of leather products requires 50 times more manpower than to produce coke and petroleum products.

Figure 4: Dependence on the number of employees at Russian industrial enterprises (2010-2015)

A similar situation is observed when considering the dependence of innovative output on pure employment. In some studies, it is proposed to use the hypothesis that the increase in output is equal to the increase in the number of employed in this production to assess the change in employment in the economy as a result of innovation (Harrison et al, 2008). This makes it possible to consider that the increase in demand for the old not innovative products of enterprises, is equal to the increase in the labour resource necessary for its production. As a result, the growth of enterprises engaged in the innovation process can be estimated as the difference between the increase in the overall level of employment in production and the increase in output of non-innovative products. The increase in employment thus calculated can be considered a pure increase in employment. When considering the growth of pure employment and the growth of output of innovative products, there is no obvious linear dependence on them. It can also be noted that the change in pure employment in most cases takes negative values (see Fig. 5), which indirectly indicates the prevalence of the displacement effect.

Figure 5: Distribution of pure employment growth of industrial Russian enterprises (2010-2015)

At the same time, the number of employees in research and development units is small; depending on the type of activity, the share of employees engaged in scientific research and development does not exceed 4%. The maximum is observed among high-tech enterprises engaged in the production of electrical equipment, electronic and optical equipment. For these activities, innovation activity is largely based on own research and development to introduce new products through product innovation. As a result, the share of sales of innovative products for this type of activity ranges from 7% to 9%, which is significantly higher than the national average.

The distribution of the number of researchers by type of economic activity is shown in Fig. 6. Thus, for most types of activities, the share of researchers does not exceed 0.4%.

Figure 6: Distribution of the share of researchers in the total number of employees of Russian industrial firms (2010-2015)

Two random forest models were trained for preliminary data analysis and identification of the most significant features. In the first case, the dynamics of the overall change in employment rate is considered as a dependent variable, while in the second case, the change in pure employment rate is considered as a dependent variable. In the first stage, the following variables are considered as attributes: sales of all products, sales of innovative and non-innovative products, costs of product innovation, cost of process innovation, costs of research and development and acquisition of machinery and equipment related to innovation, and the number of

researchers. Changes in these indicators and their specific values were also considered. Further, the pairwise correlations of the features in question were analyzed (see Fig. 7).

Figure 7: Heatmap of correlation of all considered attributes

Since many indicators are linearly dependent, nine linearly independent features have been selected for further analysis. These were: total volume of all sales, growth in sales of innovative products, growth in sales of newly introduced innovative products, costs of process innovation, growth in research and development costs, growth in costs of product innovation, growth in costs of purchasing machinery and equipment associated with innovation, the number of researchers and growth in the number of researchers. The selected features were considered as independent variables for learning the random forest model. For the first model, the growth rate of total employment calculated as a ratio of the number of employees in the current period to the number of employees in the previous period was considered as a dependent variable. Further, if there was an increase, the indicator was assigned the value +1 if the decrease is 0. When training the model, the whole sample was randomly divided into a training and a test sample, there were 33% of observations in the test sample. For training, 50 random trees were used, with the maximum depth of the tree being 5. An example of one tree is shown in Fig. 8.

Figure 8: An example of one of fifty random trees used for analysis

After training the model, it was applied on the deferred test sample, the model accuracy was 0.72. Next, the most important indicators for building the tree were selected (see Table 1). It turned out that indicators of sales of all products, growth in sales of newly introduced innovative products and growth in sales of all innovative products were used most often in tree construction. It can be noted that the importance of the indicator in the construction of the tree does not mean that its growth leads to the growth of the dependent variable. This result agrees well with the notion that changes in the number of employed people are most significantly affected by both characteristics of the overall production scale and indicators of changes in innovative output.

Table 1: Importance of indicators in model 1

Indicator	Designation	Importance
Gross sales	volume	0.19
Sales growth of newly introduced innovative products	newly_introduced_rate	0.13
Sales growth of innovative products	innov_rate	0.12
Costs of process innovation	process	0.11
Growth of number of researchers	researchers_rate	0.10
Increased costs of innovation-related machinery and equipment	equipment_rate	0.09
Increased cost of research and development	RD_rate	0.09
Increased costs of product innovation	products_rate	0.08
Number of researchers	researchers	0.07

For the second model, the pure employment change was chosen as a dependent variable, which reflects only the change in employment associated with innovative output. The training was similar to the first model and the accuracy of the second model was 0.86 on test data. The importance of the attributes is shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Importance of indicators in model 1

Indicator	Designation	importance
Increased cost of research and development	RD_rate	0.15
Gross sales	volume	0.14
Costs of process innovation	process	0.14
Sales growth of innovative products	innov_rate	0.13
Increased costs of product innovation	products_rate	0.11
Growth of number of researchers	researchers_rate	0.10
Sales growth of newly introduced innovative products	newly_introduced_rate	0.09
Increased costs of innovation-related machinery and equipment	equipment_rate	0.08
Number of researchers	researchers	0.06

The most significant indicators for dividing the sample into two classes where there was an increase or decrease in employment were indicators of growth in R&D costs, the scale of all production and the cost of process innovation.

4. Employment and output

Most industries are characterized by a decline in employment over the period from 2010 to 2015. The only exceptions are the extractive industry and activities related to the production of coke and petroleum products. Employment in these industries grew by 5% and 12%, respectively (see Table 3). There is also no significant change in the level of utilization of human resources in activities related to the production of electrical equipment, electronic and optical equipment. At the same time, the biggest drop in employment is observed in leather, leather goods and footwear production (23%), pulp and paper production (20%) and textile production (19%).

Table 3: General characteristics of changes in employment and productive activity of enterprises of different types of activities

Type of economic activity	Change of employment level (2010 2015)	Growth in non-innovative output (2010 to 2015)	Growth in innovative output (2010 to 2015)
Extraction of fuel and energy minerals	7,3%	9,7%	47%
Mining of minerals other than fuel and energy resources	0,6%	30,8%	126%
Manufacture of foodstuffs, including beverages and tobacco	-10,0%	22,1%	21%
Textile and garment manufacturing	-19,3%	-2,5%	45%
Manufacture of leather, leather goods and shoes	-22,5%	-21,1%	-18%

Type of economic activity	Change of employment level (2010 2015)	Growth in non-innovative output (2010 to 2015)	Growth in innovative output (2010 to 2015)
Wood processing and production of wood products	-16,4%	28,2%	355%
Pulp and paper production; publishing and printing activities	-20,3%	16,6%	60%
Manufacture of coke and petroleum products	12,0%	38,3%	480%
Chemical industry	-11,1%	24,8%	12%
Manufacture of rubber and plastic products	-4,9%	11,3%	94%
Manufacture of other non-metallic mineral products	-8,7%	14,7%	73%
Metallurgical production and manufacture of finished metal products	-4,5%	21,5%	103%
Manufacture of machinery and equipment	-14,1%	2,4%	-16%
Manufacture of electrical equipment, electronic and optical equipment	0,1%	30,0%	91%
Manufacture of vehicles and equipment	-3,3%	21,1%	79%
Other industries	-14,6%	33,3%	156%
Production and distribution of electricity, gas and water	-2,4%	-5,1%	3%

Despite the decline in employment over the period under study, most industries have seen an increase in non-innovative output and a significant increase in innovative production. Since output was measured in monetary terms, the producer price index by type of economic activity was used to bring the data to one base year.

Conditionally, all the considered activities can be divided into five groups depending on the ratio of labor force growth and non-innovative and innovative output. Thus, the first group includes industries where employment growth is accompanied by both conventional and innovative production. This group includes: mining, production of coconuts and oil products, and production of electrical equipment. There appears to be an expansion of production accompanied by the production of new products and the introduction of new technologies. Thus, for all branches of industry included in this group, there is an increase in the share of newly introduced or significantly improved innovative products in its total volume. There is also an increase in costs of process innovation, which indicates an attempt to improve the production base.

The second group combines industries where a decline in employment is accompanied by an increase in both conventional and innovative products. This group includes food production, wood processing, pulp and paper production, chemical production, rubber and plastic products, metallurgical production, production of other non-metallic mineral products, as well as production of vehicles and other production. It is likely that this group is characterized by the active use of both product and process innovations. At the same time, there is a prevalence of displacement effect and overcompensate effect.

The third group includes activities for which a decline in employment rates occurs against the background of increased innovative output and a decline in conventional output. This group includes textile and garment production and production and distribution of electricity, gas and water. Apparently, the main effect of the decrease in the labor force is caused by the reduction in production, despite some growth in the innovative activity of companies. The fourth group, which includes companies producing machinery and equipment, is characterized by a reduction in employment with the growth of conventional products and a decrease in the production of innovative products. The application of process innovation in this case leads to the substitution of jobs with technology. The fifth group is characterized by a decrease in employment with a decrease in all production activity. This situation is typical for the production of leather, leather goods and shoes. Compression in the industry leads to a reduction in the number of employed people.

5. Impact of innovation activity on changing employment levels

Further, regression analysis will be used to assess in more detail the impact of innovation and production activity on changes in labour use. As mentioned above, employment growth over one year for each activity in question (y) is considered as a dependent variable. The following are considered to be dependent variables: increase in conventional output (x_1), increase in innovative output (x_2), costs of technological innovation (x_3), unit cost of process innovation (x_4), unit costs of research and development of new products, services and production methods, new production processes in costs of technological innovation (x_5), increase in unit costs of machinery and equipment (x_6). The dependency is assumed to be: $y = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 x_1 + \alpha_2 x_2 + \alpha_3 x_3 + \alpha_4 x_4 + \alpha_5 x_5 + \alpha_6 x_6 + \varepsilon$

Table 4: Basic model assessment

	Dependent variable (employment growth rate)
Increase in conventional output (x_1)	0,2*** (0,035)
Increase in innovative output (x_2)	0,008* (0,004)
Costs of technological innovation (x_3)	4,7E-07*** (8,4E-08)
Unit cost of process innovation (x_4)	-0,1** (0,05)
Unit costs of research and development of new products, services and production methods, new production processes (x_5)	0,06** (0,02)
Increase in unit costs of machinery and equipment (x_6)	0,05*** (0,01)
Intercept	0,69*** (0,04)
R^2	0,72
Number of observations	85

Note: Standard errors are indicated in parentheses, "*", "**" and "***" indicate the value of the factor at 10, 5 and 1%, respectively.

As a result, it has been found that all factors except the cost of process innovation have a positive impact on employment growth (see Table 2). However, the ratio between innovative and non-innovative output growth rates is 0.04, while the average Russian ratio between innovative and non-innovative output is 4-5%. Thus, the increase in innovative and non-innovative output has the same effect on the growth of the labour force. A positive coefficient at the output growth rate of innovative products means that there is a significant overcompensate effect from product innovation when the growth in production of new products stimulates additional demand for manpower. The conclusion obtained for Russia is similar to the empirical results obtained for other countries, such as Germany (Entorf and Pohlmeier, 1990; Lachenmaier and Rottmann, 2011; Smolny, 1988), France (Greenan and Guellec, 2011) Great Britain, Spain (Harrison et al, 2008), Italy (Hall et al, 2008), South Korea (Moon, 2008). A negative coefficient for unit costs of process innovation may indicate a displacement effect caused by the introduction of new technologies. This result is also well correlated with other studies (Harrison et al, 2008; Kwon et al, 2015). At the same time, high costs of technological innovation contribute to employment growth. In other words, the positive impact of product innovation compensates for the negative impact on the number of employed process innovation and also provides for their growth. The tendency of firms to develop innovative products, services and production methods in-house is more on the development of a overcompensate effect, rather than a displacement effect. The positive impact of the increase in the cost of acquisition of machinery and equipment associated with the innovative activity of companies is a consequence of the expansion of production and also contributes to the increase in demand for manpower.

6. Conclusions

The study found the impact of different types of innovation on the changing demand for manpower. It found that the growth of innovative products (product innovation) has a positive impact on changing employment levels in the economy. However, the same increase in the volume of innovative and non-innovative production requires an equal increase in the number of people employed to produce innovative and conventional products. This situation may be related to the fact that a large share of the growth of innovative output is occupied by modernized products, the production which does not require significant changes in the production base, i.e., large-scale introduction of process innovations. This means that the expansion of conventional production requires the involvement of new manpower to the same extent as that of innovative production.

The paper also shows that in modern conditions the increase in costs of process innovations in industrial enterprises leads to a significant amount of substitution of labor resources with capital. Unfortunately, the previous result shows that these process innovations are not radical enough to significantly renew production and thus ensure the production of innovative products of high quality (Samovoleva, 2019).

In addition, it should be noted that, depending on the ratio of changes in employment to output of conventional and innovative products, all activities can be roughly divided into five groups. The first group includes industries with increasing employment and output of both innovative and conventional products. This group is characterized by an expansion in production accompanied by the production of new products and the introduction of technologies. The second group is characterized by a decline in employment, accompanied by an increase in the production of both innovative and conventional products. Both product and process innovations are actively used here, with the displacement effect caused by the latter being dominant.

The third group includes activities for which the decline in employment occurs against the background of the growth of innovative output and the decline in the production of conventional products. In this case, the main effect of a decrease in the labour force is due to a reduction in output, despite some innovation activity in the group. The fourth group is characterized by a decrease in employment with the growth of production activity as a whole and a decrease in the volume of innovative products. The application of process innovation in this case can lead to a displacement effect, where jobs are replaced by technology. The fifth group is characterized by lower employment levels with lower overall productive activity. A reduction in the industry's production leads to a reduction in employment. The cumulative effect of all these groups leads to the effects described above.

References

- Balycheva, Y., Golichenko, O. (2015) "The innovation process of Russian manufacturing companies", Proceedings of the 10th European Conference on Innovation and Entrepreneurship, ECIE 2015, 2015.
- Balycheva, Y., Samovoleva, S. (2019) "Innovative businesses in Russian science cities", ECIE 2019, pp. 110-116.
- Entorf, H., Pohlmeier, W. (1990) Innovation, Employment and Export Activity: Evidence From Firm-level Data.
- Greenan, N., Guellec, D. (2011) "Technological innovation and employment reallocation", *Labour*, 14 (4), 547–590.
- Hall, B.H., Lotti, F., Mairesse, J. (2008) "Employment, innovation, and productivity: evidence from Italian microdata", *Ind. Corp. Chang.*, 17 (4), 813–839.
- Harrison, R., Jamandreu, J., Mairesse, J. (2014) "Does innovation stimulate employment? A firm-level analysis using comparable micro-data from four European countries", *International Journal Ind. Organ.*, 35, 29–43.
- Harrison, R., Jamandreu, J., Mairesse, J. (2008) "Does Innovation Stimulate Employment? A Firm-level Analysis Using Comparable Micro-data From Four European Countries", *National Bureau of Economic Research*.
- Industrial production in Russia (2016), Federal state statistics service.
- Kwon, S.J., Park, E., Ohm, J.Y., Yoo, K. (2015) "Innovation Activities and the Creation of New Employment: An Empirical Assessment of South Korea's Manufacturing Industry", *Social Science Information*.
- Lachenmaier, S., Rottmann, H. (2011) "Effects of innovation on employment: a dynamic panel analysis", *Int. J. Ind. Organ.*, 29 (2), 210–220.
- Moon, S.B., Chun, H.B. (2008) "The effects of innovation activities on employment: evidence from Korean ICT firms", *Korean Journal of Industrial Organization*, 16 (1), 1–24.
- Samovoleva, S.A. (2019) "Technological knowledge absorption as a factor of innovation development", *Voprosy Ekonomiki*, (11) pp. 150-158. (In Russ).
- Samovoleva, S., Balycheva, Y. (2018), "Absorptive capacity as a factor of firms' innovative behaviour", ECIE 2018, pp. 709-716.
- Seidl da Fonseca R. (2017) "The Future of Employment: evaluating the impact of STI foresight exercises", *Foresight and STI Governance*, vol. 11, no 4, pp.9-22.
- Smolny, W. (1988) "Innovations, prices and employment: a theoretical model and an empirical application for West German manufacturing firms" *J. Ind. Econ.*, 46 (3), 359–381.
- Vivarelli M. (2014) "Innovation, employment and skills in advanced and developing countries: a survey of economic literature", *Journal of Economics Issues*, 48 (1), pp.123–154.
- Вешкурова, А. Б., Пономарев, М.А., Копылова Н.А. (2017) "Влияние экономики инновационного типа на занятость населения", *Экономика и управление: проблемы, решения*. Т.2, №8., с. 5-11.
- Голиченко, О.Г., Бальчева, Ю.Е. (2010) "Выбор рыночной стратегии использования интеллектуальной собственности российскими предприятиями", *Экономическая наука современной России*, №4(51), с. 68-82.
- Капелюшников, Р. (2017) "Технологический прогресс - пожиратель рабочих мест?", *Вопросы экономики*, 2017, № 11.